

Machine Learning Applications on Neuroimaging For Diagnosis And Prognosis Of Epilepsy

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Abstract—Machine learning is becoming more significant in medical image processing, resulting in new improvements in neuroimaging clinical applications. A failure in brain functioning causes epileptic seizures, which can have a catastrophic impact on the patient's well-being. For medication-assisted seizure prevention, predicting the onset of epileptic seizures before they begin is critical. Machine learning approaches and computational methodologies are used to predict epileptic seizures by employing electroencephalogram (EEG) recordings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Epilepsy is a central nervous system (CNS) illness that affects roughly 1.2 percent of the population in the United States (3.4 million individuals) and more than 65 million people worldwide. Furthermore, one out of every 26 people will get epilepsy at some point in their lives. Seizures come in a variety of forms, each with its own set of symptoms, such as loss of consciousness, jerking movements, or bewilderment. Some seizures are significantly more difficult to detect visually; patients frequently show signs like not reacting or staring blankly for a short amount of time. Seizures can strike at any time, causing injuries such as stumbling, biting the tongue, or losing control of one's pee or stool.

As a result, these are some of the reasons why seizure detection is critical for patients who are under medical monitoring and are suspected of having seizures.

This research will employ binary classification algorithms to predict whether a person is having a seizure based on their EEG.

The method for detecting epilepsy that uses:

- Feature Engineering: For our machine learning system, feature engineering is the process of converting categorical or ordinal characteristics into machine-readable numerical variables.

- Binary Classification Algorithms: Binary classification issues may be solved using machine learning methods spanning from Naive Bayes to deep learning networks. In terms of runtime and accuracy, the data volume (number of samples and attributes) and data quality indicate which approach is better (outliers, imbalanced data).

II. MOTIVATION

Seizures come in a variety of forms, each with its own set of symptoms, such as loss of consciousness, jerking movements, or bewilderment. Some seizures are significantly more difficult to detect visually; patients frequently show signs like not reacting or staring blankly for a short amount of time. Seizures can strike at any time, causing injuries such as stumbling, biting the tongue, or losing control of one's pee or stool. As a result, these are some of the reasons why seizure detection is critical for patients who are under medical monitoring and are suspected of having seizures. This research will employ binary classification algorithms to predict whether a person is having a seizure or not. Thus through early detection of epilepsy, we can prevent seizures early on.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Jie Yuan et al. proposes two techniques to applying machine learning methods to neuroimaging data: i) traditional machine learning, which combines manual feature engineering and classifiers, and ii) deep learning, which uses convolutional neural networks and autoencoders.[1]

Syed Muhammad Usman et al. For epileptic seizures, patients appear to be in a anticipated state. To forecast epileptic episodes, machine learning models are utilized. EEG signal capture, signal preprocessing, signal feature extraction, and classification between distinct seizure states are all included in these machine learning models.[2]

Peyvand Ghaderyan et al. In this work, an optimal innovative strategy is proposed for removing computational

complexity and clinically predicting epileptic seizures. It is based on eight frequency sub-bands' univariate linear characteristics. It also uses principal component analysis (PCA) to reduce dimensions and select the best characteristics.[3]

Ahmet Alkan et al. algorithm depends on logistic regression (LR) and the developing computationally efficient methods based on artificial neural networks are two fundamentally distinct approaches for creating classification models (classifiers) (ANNs). Classifiers based on LR and multilayer perceptron neural networks (MLPNN) were constructed and compared in terms of their accuracy in classifying EEG signals.[4]

Remy Ben Messaoud & Mario Chavez provides a Machine Learning-based epileptic seizure prediction approach that beats current methods. Using the Random Forest classifier, we evaluate the chance of being anticipated versus interictal for a particular epoch and incorporate new ideas to improve the algorithm's robustness towards false alarms.[5]

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find a Machine Learning model to identify whether the person having epilepsy or not with the dataset. The dataset is divided into three training, validating and testing data sets. The model should be trained with more data to get accuracy in learning.

A. Data Collection: The dataset contains 4097 electroencephalogram (EEG) readings collected during 23.5 seconds from 500 individuals. The 4097 data points were then divided into 23 chunks, each matching to a sole row in the dataset. Each row has 178 readings, which are then transformed into columns; to put it another way, one second of EEG data contains 178 columns. There are 11,500 rows and 179 columns in all, with the end column indicating whether the patient is having a seizure or not. [1]

B. Model Selection: Model selection refers to the process of determining a single machine learning model for a training dataset from a pool of candidate machine learning models. Model selection is a technique that can be applied to a variety of models (e.g. logistic regression, SVM, KNN, etc.)

1. **KNN** – KNN stands for K Nearest Neighbor, and it's a classification model that divides a sample into classes based on the k samples closest to it. If $k=3$ and all three samples closest to the sample in question are class 1, the sample in question will also be categorized as class 1. If two of the three samples closest to the one in question are class 1, the sample in question has a 66 percent chance of being categorized as class 1.[3]
2. **Logistic Regression** – Logistic regression is an extension of ordinary linear models' concepts and abilities. By projecting the sample points onto the line, logistic regression performs a linear function

on your input features. The linear function is used in form of generalized linear model, which is an by adding the log of likelihood of each sample point and optimizing the log of likelihood, which is the same as maximizing the likelihood, to obtain the best-fitting logistic regression line. In a binary classification model, the best fitting function would anticipate the probability of the positive class to be really near to 1 (100 percent), and the probability of the negative class to be close to 0.[4]

3. **Stochastic Gradient Descent** - Gradient descent is a method for minimizing a large number of loss functions in a variety of models, including linear regression, logistic regression, and clustering models. In a linear regression model, GD plots all potential sums of squared residuals and calculates the slope by taking the derivative of the slope at the chosen point. The lowest slope of the curve is fined by GD, which in linear regression is when the derivative is 0. In other models, gradient descent finds the smallest slope by making big estimates at first and smaller guesses as it gets closer to the minimal value; this makes gradient descent highly useful for solving for where the derivative equals 0.[1]
4. **Naïve Bayes** - The Bayes theorem is used by the naive Bayes classifier to perform classification. It is assumed that if all features are unrelated, the likelihood of seeing them all together is equal to the product of the probabilities of each feature occurring separately. It calculates the likelihood of each feature for each class. If one of our features is weather outlook, and our dependent variable is whether or not we will play golf, we will calculate the likelihood of each weather outlook category based on whether or not we will play. We multiply all of these numbers together using these results. This yields a result that represents the probability of X given a class multiplied by a class's probability. $P(X|C)P(C)$. This is done for both classes, and then both sides are divided by $P(X)$ to be normalized. Finally, we assess the normalized probability of scenario X given its class to determine whether or not we will classify a sample under it. The sample will then be categorized under the class with the higher probability.[1]
5. **Decision Tree Classifier** - A decision tree categorizes the sample based on the answer. The classification can be numeric or categorical. The classifying method divides data into sub regions of the same class repeatedly, and the tree ends when the algorithm has divided all samples into pure classes, or when some of the classifier[1]
6. **Random Forest** - By bootstrapping the collection of samples or employing a random amount of features at each split, a random forest is created by

bagging decision trees that are not associated with each other. RF combines the simplicity of decision trees with the flexibility of RF, resulting in a significant increase in accuracy, which is one of decision trees' flaws as a classifier.

Step I: Create a bootstrapped dataset first. We can choose the same sample multiple times.

Step II: Using the bootstrapped dataset, design a decision tree with only a random subset of variables at each node.

Step III: Create a new tree and repeat step 1 with a new bootstrapped dataset. Create at least 100 trees if possible.[5]

7. **Gradient Boosting Classifier** - We begin with a leaf that represents an initial forecast for each individual; the log(odds), which is the logistic regression equivalent of the average, is the first prediction for each individual. If four people have diabetes and two do not, the log(odds) is $\log(4/2) = 0.7$, which we place in the first leaf. The log(odds) is then converted into a probability using a logistic function. We can classify everyone in the training dataset as having diabetes because the likelihood of having diabetes is larger than 0.5 (we may also choose another number). However, labelling everyone in the dataset as diabetic is pointless because two persons do not have diabetes.

8. **Extremely Random Trees** - The ExtraTrees Classifier is comparable to the Random Forest Classifier except for the following:

Instead of bootstrapping samples, samples are obtained from the complete training set when choosing a variable at the split.

Instead than being specified as in Random Forest, node splits are chosen at random.[2]

9. **XGBoost Classifier** - XGBoost is akin to gradient boosting but

- The number of terminal nodes in a tree varies.
- The leaf weights of trees whose leaf weights are estimated with less evidence are reduced more.
- Compared to gradient descent, Newton Boosting gives a direct path to the minima.
- To lessen the correlation between trees, an additional randomization parameter is utilized.
- Because ordinary GBM has no regularisation, it uses a more regularised model to control over-fitting, which offers it a higher performance than GBM.

- XGB uses parallel processing and is significantly quicker than GBM.[2]

Model Evaluation: Model selection is the process of choosing a single machine learning model for a training dataset from a set of candidate machine learning models. Model selection is a technique that can be applied to a variety of models (e.g. logistic regression, SVM, KNN, etc.) [1]

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The model building is the main step in the epilepsy detection. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import pandas as pd
import pickle
import KNeighborsClassifier
import LogisticRegression
import SGDCClassifier
import GaussianNB
import DecisionTreeClassifier
import RandomForestClassifier
import GradientBoostingClassifier
```

2. Add the data into a DataFrame,, then get the shape of data.

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded=files.upload()
df = pd.read_csv("data.csv")
```


Fig 1. Imported Dataset

3. Then split the dataset into training and testing datasets.

```
df_data = df_data.sample(n=len(df_data))
df_data = df_data.reset_index(drop=True)
df_valid_test = df_data.sample(frac=0.3)
```

```
print("Validation/Test Split Size:
%.1f" % (len(df_valid_test) / len(df_data)))
'accuracy':[knn_train_accuracy,
knn_valid_accuracy,lr_train_accuracy,lr_valid_accu
racy,sgdc_train_accuracy,sgdc_valid_accuracy,nb_train_
accuracy,nb_valid_accuracy,tree_train_accuracy,tree_
valid_accuracy,rf_train_accuracy,rf_valid_accurac
y,gbc_train_accuracy,gbc_valid_accuracy,xgbc_train_
accuracy,xgbc_valid_accuracy,etc_train_accuracy,et
c_valid_accuracy],
df_test = df_valid_test.sample(frac=0.5)
df_valid = df_valid_test.drop(df_test.index)
```

```
df_train_all = df_data.drop(df_valid_test.index)
```

```
Validation/Test Split Size: 0.3
```

Fig 2. Dataset Split Size

4. Then, select the model

```
etc = ExtraTreesClassifier(bootstrap=False,
criterion="entropy", max_features=1.0,
min_samples_leaf=3,
min_samples_split=20, n_estimators=100)
etc.fit(X_train_tf, y_train)
y_train_preds = etc.predict_proba(X_train_tf)[:, 1]
y_valid_preds = etc.predict_proba(X_valid_tf)[:, 1]
print('Extra Trees Classifier')
print('Training:')
etc_train_auc, etc_train_accuracy, etc_train_recall,
etc_train_precision, \
etc_train_specificity = print_report(y_train,
y_train_preds, thresh)
print('Validation:')
etc_valid_auc, etc_valid_accuracy, etc_valid_recall,
etc_valid_precision, \
etc_valid_specificity = print_report(y_valid,
y_valid_preds, thresh)
```

```
Extra Trees Classifier
Training:
AUC:1.000
accuracy:0.997
recall:0.999
precision:0.996
specificity:0.996
prevalence:0.500
Validation:
AUC:0.991
accuracy:0.962
recall:0.966
precision:0.864
specificity:0.961
prevalence:0.205
```

Fig 3. Model Selection

5. Analyze results baseline models

```
df_results =
pd.DataFrame({'classifier':['KNN','KNN','LR','LR','S
GD','SGD','NB','NB','DT','DT','RF','RF','GB','GB','X
GBC','XGBC','ETC','ETC'],
'data_set':['train','valid']*9,
'auc':[knn_train_auc,knn_valid_auc,lr_train_auc,lr_v
alid_auc,sgdc_train_auc,sgdc_valid_auc,nb_train_au
c,nb_valid_auc,tree_train_auc,tree_valid_auc,rf_train_
auc,rf_valid_auc,gbc_train_auc,gbc_valid_auc,xgbc_
_train_auc,
xgbc_valid_auc,etc_train_auc,etc_valid_auc],
'recall':[knn_train_recall,
knn_valid_recall,lr_train_recall,lr_valid_recall,sgdc_train_r
ecall,sgdc_valid_recall,nb_train_recall,nb_valid_recall,tree_
train_recall,tree_valid_recall,rf_train_recall,rf_valid_recall,
gbc_train_recall,gbc_valid_recall,xgbc_train_recall,xgbc_va
lid_recall,etc_train_recall,etc_valid_recall],
'precision':[knn_train_precision,
knn_valid_precision,lr_train_precision,lr_valid_precision,sg
dc_train_precision,sgdc_valid_precision,nb_train_precision,
nb_valid_precision,tree_train_precision,tree_valid_precision
,rf_train_precision,rf_valid_precision,gbc_train_precision,g
bc_valid_precision,xgbc_train_precision,xgbc_valid_precisi
on,etc_train_precision,etc_valid_precision],
'specificity':[knn_train_specificity,
knn_valid_specificity,lr_train_specificity,lr_valid_specificit
y,sgdc_train_specificity,sgdc_valid_specificity,nb_train_spe
cificity,nb_valid_specificity,tree_train_specificity,tree_valid_
specificity,rf_train_specificity,rf_valid_specificity,gbc_train_
specificity,gbc_valid_specificity,xgbc_train_specificity,x
gbc_valid_specificity,etc_train_specificity,etc_valid_specifi
city]})
```


Fig 4. Model Analyze

- [4] Alkan, Ahmet & Koklukaya, Etem & Subasi, Abdulhamit . Automatic seizure detection in EEG using logistic regression and artificial neural network. 2020
- [5] Remy Ben Messaoud & Mario Chavez . Random Forest classifier for EEG-based seizure prediction,2020

VI. RESULT

The result shows the true positive rate and False Positive rate with high accuracy.

VII. CONCLUSION

Here I have selected the best model by assessing their accuracy, precision, recall and specificity. When compared to a random choice targeting model, lift is a measure of how well a targeting model (association rule) predicts or classifies situations as having an elevated response (in comparison to the population as a whole). The best model has a lift performance of 4.3, which means it is 4.3 times better than guessing at random. It also correctly predicts the positive classes in the test set 97.4% of the time. If this model were used to predict whether or not a patient is experiencing a seizure, you may expect it to do well in correctly predicting those who are having one. This helps seizures to be detected at an early phase, which in turn makes its treatment easier and more cost-effective.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Jie Yuan¹, Xuming Ran¹, Keyin Liu¹, Chen Yao² . Machine Learning Applications on Neuroimaging for Diagnosis and Prognosis of Epilepsy: A Review,2021
- [2] Syed Muhammad Usman, Muhammad Usman,¹ and Simon Fong² . Epileptic Seizures Prediction Using Machine Learning Methods,2020
- [3] Ghaderyan, Peyvand & Abbasi, Ata & Sedaaghi, Mohammad. An efficient seizure prediction method using KNN-based undersampling and linear frequency measures,2020